

Relationship among Vocational Courses in Higher Education and Skill Development in India

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Abstract

In present scenario all service sectors demand a skilled individual. The time had gone when only our degree or qualification were the deciding factors for getting the job. Now there is the need of the individuals who are not just qualified but also who are skilled to handle the things in practical situations. Because the present scenario has been totally transformed with the technological innovations. And the vocational courses are the key component to produce skill and competent individuals. The skill development of any country relies on the quality of vocational courses that they offer because vocational courses and skill development are interrelated with each other. In India literacy rate is improving day by day but if we look at the percentage of skilled individuals, it is still very low. There are large numbers of people who are educated but not skilled and trained. There are various factors that are creating the gap between training and actual work life context. The lack of skills among individuals is the main reason of problems like unemployment and less economic growth in India. In India there is a lack of supply and demand of skilled individuals because our global world calls for a large numbers of competent individuals but our country is unable to fulfill this demand. This is the need of the hour to rethink the skill development in India. There should be recreation facilities for the students so that students can nurture their skills and from the very beginning there should be provision of vocational training and the vocational trainings must reflect the need of real life context. The skill development is also the Key focus of NEP 2020 as it also aims at developing the practical skills of individual's. So the present paper will explore the relationship between vocational courses and the skill development in India. Further it also emphasizes on the challenges coming in the way of skill development.

Keywords: Competent, Development, Skills, Training, Vocational Courses.

Introduction

Skills are the basic demanding components of every sector and now a day's skills are very much required for being successful in any field. Only having good qualification is not enough to survive in this dynamic world. Being skilled means having competency, ability and Knowledge (technical, practical, conceptual) and having the spirit of making or adopting new innovations. One can acquire these skills through training or through experience. If we talk about India there is a big gap between training given by institutions and the actual work context. Most of the training institutions in India are not able to meet the requirements of global world because they have not equipped their institutions with the resources required to deal with global knowledge and skills. There are also many challenges before these institutions that prevent them to compete with this ever changing world. In India still most of the people confuse qualification with skills. They are striving for getting the highest qualification, so that they can get a good job. They don't recognize that qualification without having practical skills is useless. While striving for qualification, they forget to nurture their strengths and skills that they are having. This is the reason why India is facing so many problems like

unemployment, low economic rate, poverty etc. Every work field is adopting technological innovations at a very fast pace, so it requires skilled and competent individual to deal with the coming innovations but due to lack of skills, even the most qualified youth is unemployed and thus leading to the lower economic rate of the country. As per studies, it has been found that the large number of youth is present in India and we all know that youth has the power to strengthen our nation but due to improper channelization of their energy, lack of skills and lack of direction, the youth of our country is unable to give the desired outputs. And the skill development totally depends upon the vocational courses that various educational institutions offer to their students. But in India generally vocational education is being given students at higher classes but it should be provided from the most initial stages of the school. The NEP 2020 have also addressed this issue and have recommend that vocational education should be given to the students from the 6th standard itself. So that from the early years of child he/she began to develop his skills that he need to perform his/her job and to earn his /her livelihood. In India there are only few areas which focus on Vocational education like ITI colleges, other engineering colleges etc. In Other areas, there

is less emphasis on technical and vocational education. We should understand that other areas also need technical and practical skills. Like if we talk about teachers there are so many professional courses for them but most of the teachers still don't have adequate skills to deal with 21st century world. Thus we can say that there are so many gaps between skill development and vocational courses in India.

Objectives

1. To explore the relationship between vocational education and skill development in India.
2. To identify the challenges coming in the way of skill development in India.
3. To analyze the NEP 2020 in relation to the skill development in India.
4. To find out the appropriate measures for strengthening and reshaping the skill development in India.

Methodology

1. The study is based on the Secondary Sources.
2. The data were collected from the Journals, Websites and Various Research Papers.

Discussion:

India Needs To Reshape The Skill Development

1. To strengthen the economy of the country.
2. To deal with the global world.
3. To enhance the productivity in every area of work.
4. To create congruence between the demand and supply of skilled individuals.
5. To deal with the problem of unemployment in India.
6. To bring the feeling of satisfaction among employees.

Vocational Courses In India

1. Electronics
2. Engineering
3. Computer Training
4. Certificate Courses
5. Data Handling Courses.
6. Medical Related Courses and Many More.

But vocational courses in India needs to be strengthened more by maintaining balance between what is being taught in those courses and what actually is required in the field. And only those certificate courses should be considered valid that are completed from the recognized universities so that the mismatch between the certificates and the actual knowledge can be diminished.

Nep 2020 And Skill Development

The NEP 2020 is a great initiative to strengthen the skill development in India as it aims to develop the 21st century skills, scientific temperament, problem solving skills and critical thinking among individuals. NEP 2020 focuses on experiential learning, so that students can get proficient skills while engaging themselves in experiential learning. It doesn't support traditional

rote learning methods but it support the methods which help them in practical life situations. NEP 2020 has also emphasized to develop digital literacy among individuals so that individuals can get required skills to deal with technological innovations. So NEP 2020 is a great initiative for reshaping the skill development in India. It has addressed adequately the needs of reshaping skill development. Proper implementation of the NEP 2020 will surely strengthen the skill development in India.

Challenges Coming In The Way Of Skill Development

1. Less Investment in Raising Human Capital:

Human resources are the precious capital for the country. They are the biggest asset of our country. But as comparison to other countries, our country invests very less amount in education sector and technical education field. So our country needs to invest more in Educational field.

2. Inadequate Infrastructure: There is a lack of infrastructure in our country which needs for accessing the skill education. Most of the institutions doesn't have proper infrastructure that can helps the individuals in developing their skills.

3. Women Skill Development In Rural Areas:

There is no doubt that women in India are very progressive and they are successfully dealing with the world But in some rural areas they don't get access to technical or skill education even if they are interested. Somewhere thinking of the society and somewhere lack of access to resources becomes a barrier for women skill development. It also needs to address properly.

4. Label of Government Job: In India there is a thinking that label of government job is very much important. People give less emphasis to start their own work in which they are interested and skilled. It is found in very studies that people of China are very skilled and they don't only rely on government jobs instead they do their own work. It is the result that many countries use their products and other so many things. So our youth also needs to understand that starting their own work in which they are skilled is fine. It's not compulsory to have the label of government job.

5. Qualification and Skill Education: In India most of the people still don't understand the difference between qualification and skill education. These types of people need to be addressed properly.

6. Practical Training: India's vocational or professional courses still don't provide practical work experience to the individuals. So India need to put more emphasis on practical training.

7. Poverty: Poverty is also a challenge for the individuals that prevent them to have proper skill education.

Recommendations

- Most of the students don't know about the various initiatives and schemes that are made for developing the skills of Individuals . They should be provided with the adequate knowledge about various skill enhancement schemes.
- Educational institutions should try to develop the soft skills of the learners because soft skills are very much important now days for being successful in any field.
- Today's parents also expect from their children to get good marks in the examination. They rarely bother that their child is developing his/her skills are not. So parents should also put emphasis to develop the skill of the children rather only focusing on marks.
- The teachers should be posted according to sanctioned posts.
- There is an urgent need to introduce more vocational courses in rural areas.
- Most of the training institutions select the trainers who are having highest qualification. They should recruit the trainers who are having skills rather than only qualification.
- During vocational education, individuals should be given opportunity to work in real context.
- Appropriate resources should be built in training institutions so that individuals who are engaged in training can get required resources for developing their skills.
- Ongoing professional training should not only be compulsory for teachers but it should be compulsory for every sector.
- Training institutions should develop the training programmes after analyzing the needs of Global World.
- Efforts should be made to develop the skills of distance learners also.
- Proper implementation of proposed schemes related to skill development.

Conclusion

Laconically we can say that Vocational courses are very much related with the skill development, so vocational courses should be properly planned and there should be provision of actual work experience in every vocational course .we all need to rethink for developing the skills among the youth of India. We need to channelize their skills properly for getting desired results and a collaborative effort is required to address the challenges of skill development in India. All the citizens of India need to understand that mere

qualification is not enough for being successful but it requires competency and skills for becoming successful in the global world.

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